

Bioactive Wollastonite synthesized by sol-gel combustion method by using tartaric acid as a fuel for bone regenerative applications

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Abstract : Wollastonite (CaSiO_3) has received its consideration in the field of hard tissue engineering due to its good bioactivity and biocompatibility. In the present study, Wollastonite was prepared by sol-gel combustion method by using tartaric acid as a fuel for the first time. Calcium nitrate and tetraethyl orthosilicate were taken as the source of calcium and silicate. The obtained product was characterised by FT-IR spectroscopy to identify the characteristic functional groups present in the material and powder X-Ray diffraction technique for the phase identification. The SEM image reveals that the morphology of Wollastonite which was irregular in shape and particles are homogeneous in size.

Keywords : Wollastonite, biocompatibility, X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy.

Introduction

Wollastonite, a common ceramic material contains 48.28% CaO and 51.72% SiO_2 found abundance in metamorphosed lime stone. It finds potential application such as dielectric material, glaze and flux, lining bricks, porcelain material, sanitary component and as radioceramics^{1,2}. In the branch of hard tissue engineering, many authors focused on the bone regenerative property of Wollastonite due to its bioactivity, biocompatibility and the potency to develop hydroxyl apatite layer on implantation, a necessary criteria for all the bioactive ceramics used in clinical application. The rate of deposition of apatite layer on its surface in a cellular simulated body fluid is faster than the available bioactive ceramics like hydroxyapatite and tricalcium phosphate ceramics^{3,4}.

Solid state method like conventional synthesis leads to obtain the product at very high temperature and results in

the formation of crystalline compounds. Synthesis route plays a very important role in the field of its application. We adopted a synthesis method which combines sol-gel method and combustion technique which makes the formation of compound with interconnected porous structures, with this morphology Wollastonite possesses very good bioactivity comparable with synthetic routes such as solid state and co-precipitation technique⁵⁻⁸.

In the current study, bioactive Wollastonite was synthesized by the sol-gel combustion method by using tartaric acid as a complexing agent for the first time. This methodology favours the formation of porous microstructure ceramic material which is expected to do rapid deposition of apatite layer on its surface.

Results and discussion

Tartaric acid played two major role in this sol-gel

Scheme 1. Preparation of Wollastonite by sol-gel combustion method using tartaric acid as a fuel.

assisted combustion synthesis. Firstly, it makes the homogeneous mixing of the solution by forming the complexes with the metal cations. Secondly, it involves in the reduction of nitrates and liberates enormous amount of heat during combustion process at 400 °C. This excess energy facilitates the removal of organic content of the fuel present in the dried gel and favours the formation of precursor.

The FT-IR spectrum (Fig. 1a) of the dried gel shows the stretching vibration of C=O group of carboxylate ion occurs in the frequency region 1621 cm⁻¹⁹. This reveals that the calcium ion complexes with the carboxylate ion of the tartaric acid. The peak at 1381 cm⁻¹ is due to the stretching vibration of nitrate ions present in the dried gel¹⁰. Simultaneously the hydrolysis of TEOS (tetraethyl orthosilicate) takes place leads to the formation of Si-OH groups. The bands at 1144 cm⁻¹ is due to the Si-O-Si linkages gained after the polycondensation process among those Si-OH groups. The peaks observed at 960 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the unpolymerized Si-OH linkages left out in the dried gel¹¹.

The FT-IR spectrum (Fig. 1b) of precursor obtained after combustion process is expected to contain CaCO₃ and SiO₂. The characteristic bands at 1456 cm⁻¹ is due to the out of plane bending vibration and the band at 875 cm⁻¹ is due to the asymmetric stretching vibration of

carbonate ions^{12,13}. The peak assigned at 1041 cm⁻¹ is due to the Si-O-Si asymmetric bond stretching vibrations and 714 cm⁻¹ is because of the symmetric Si-O-Si stretching vibrations.

The FT-IR spectrum (Fig. 1c) corresponds to the prepared Wollastonite powders. The peak around 900–950 cm⁻¹ is assigned due to the Si-O-Ca bonds containing non bridging oxygen atoms. The band observed in the lower frequency region like 521 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the bending mode of vibration of O-Si-O linkage^{14,15}.

Fig. 2 shows the powder XRD pattern of Wollastonite synthesized by using tartaric acid at the calcination temperature of 900 °C for 12 h. The PXRD pattern of Wollastonite is matched accordance with the standard JCPDS file No. 00-043-1460. The average grain size is calculated using Scherrer's formula and it is found to be 55.8 nm. The crystal system is monoclinic and lattice parameter values calculated by from the XRD pattern were $a = 15.4325 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 7.3248 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 7.0725 \text{ \AA}$. The prepared Wollastonite is found to be single phasic without any impurities of other calcium phases of silicates.

SEM images (Fig. 3a) of Wollastonite shows highly agglomerated particles with high porosity. The pore size of the particle ranges from 0.5–0.8 μm. Also the interconnectivity of the pores are observed (Fig. 3a) on

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectra of (a) dried gel, (b) precursor and (c) Wollastonite.

Fig. 2. PXRD pattern of the as synthesized Wollastonite.

the surface of the particles which plays a major role in the bioactivity process. Fig. 3b shows that Wollastonite possesses coral like morphology.

Fig. 3. SEM image of Wollastonite (a) with highly porous particles and (b) coral like morphology.

Experimental

Precursor obtained by the tartaric acid gel process :

Calcium nitrate tetrahydrate (99%, SD Fine, AR) and tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS (98%, Acros Organics, AR)) were used as the starting material. Tartaric acid (99.5%, SD Fine, AR) is used as chelating agent and also as a fuel. Stoichiometric ratios of 1 M aqueous solution of calcium nitrate, 1 M aqueous solution of tartaric acid were thoroughly mixed using a magnetic stirrer. 4.5 mL of TEOS was added to the mixture and the nitric acid was added to catalyse the formation of polymeric gel net-

work. A thick transparent gel was formed after continuous mixing for 3 h heated to the temperature of 60 °C. The formed gel was dried at 150 °C for 2 h. The dried gel was combusted in a muffle furnace at 400 °C to form the greyish black colour precursor. The formed precursor was finely powdered by using agate mortar and pestle. The precursor obtained after combustion process was calcined at 900 °C for 12 h to form single phasic Wollastonite.

Characterization :

FT-IR spectrum was recorded by using Shimadzu (TR Affinity 1) spectrophotometer in the range of 500 to 4000 cm^{-1} by the KBr pellet method. The phase identification of the product was performed on Bruker D8 Advance powder X-ray diffractometer. Morphological analysis was carried out using Hitachi S-3400 scanning electron microscope.

Conclusion

Bioceramic Wollastonite is synthesized by a cost effective and simple methodology by using tartaric acid as a fuel for the first time by sol-gel combustion method. Wollastonite powder is prepared at lesser processing temperature and time by this technique. The product formed is found to possess high porosity which is very much required to possess a bioactivity.

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